

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6628870

DISORDERS OF MOTOR SYSTEM AND ATTENTION OF PERMANENTLY RESIDING ADOLESCENTS IN ANTHROPOGENICALLY POLLUTED REGIONS OF GEORGIA

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Abstract. In Georgian important cities and regions (Batumi, Kutaisi, Tbilisi, Rustavi, Marneuli) the level of xenobiotics in young people's blood is ≥ 5.0 mcg/dl. But by young people who permanently resided in high contaminated with xenobiotic regions the level in blood is marked higher than ≤ 10.0 mcg/dl. The aim of the work was to determine of visual-motor and visual-spatial evidence development by young people permanently resided in anthropogenic contaminated regions with xenobiotic and find correlation between the age (the range is 19-22 years) and level of xenobiotics in blood: the range of $Pl \geq 5.0$ mcg/dl in I study group and ≤ 10.0 mcg/dl in II study group. Control group has no xenobiotics in blood. Luria-Christensen neuropsychological and visual-motor and visual-spatial evidence by WBAVMA methods are used. According to our results we have concluded the correlation between constantly resided in anthropogenic contaminated regions young people's age and level of xenobiotics in blood.

Keywords: Ecologically unfavourable regions, xenobiotic.

Introduction. The concept of "ecological pathology" has expanded our understanding of the importance of anthropogenic pollution, primarily in the growth and physical development of adolescents. According to the available data ^[1], in many regions of Georgia, the level of anthropogenic pollution in drinking water, air and soil does not exceed the permissible norms, but according to the existing notion, the impact of anthropogenic pollution is related to the prevalence of environmental toxicity, as well as to the length of exposure, which has primary or secondary effect on the process of physical and mental development of a person. According to the percentage of cases studied, in some regions of Georgia (Kvemo Kartli, Mtskheta-Tianeti, Kakheti, Imereti, Samegrelo) the volume of xenobiotics in the blood of the permanently residing people does not exceed ≥ 5.0 mcg/dl, but in some regions and cities, xenobiotics levels reaches and exceeds ≥ 5.0 mcg/dl (Kakheti - 4.0%; Shida Kartli - 5.0%; Kvemo Kartli - 6.0%; Mtskheta-Tianeti - 6.0%; Tbilisi - 7.0%; Samegrelo, Zemo Svaneti - 27%; Adjara - 50.0% according to the percentage of cases studied). ^[3] According to the National Center for Disease Control and Public Health ^[2], intoxication caused by soil dust is a subject of consideration along with nutritional exposure. Thus, an increase in lead content in the environment for every 100.0 mcg/dl leads to its increase in human blood of 0.5 - 1.6 mcg/dl. Contrary to popular belief, ^[2] despite having a blood lead level of 5.0 mcg/dl, the so-called "safety" level, any level of xenobiotics in the blood is unacceptable. At present, the toxic effects of anthropogenically polluted regions of Georgia on the physical and mental development of the adolescent population have not been sufficiently studied.

Objectives. The aim of this research is to study a clinical symptoms of motor system and attention deficit disorders in consideration of level of xenobiotics (Pb) in blood in adolescent population of anthropogenically polluted regions (Tbilisi, Batumi, Marneuli, Rustavi) of Georgia. In each case, the level of xenobiotics in the blood of the studied contingent according to anthropogenically contaminated regions is considered, which allows to determine the possible connection between motor system and attention disorders and the blood content of xenobiotics.

Materials and methods. The adolescent population studied is divided into three groups based on the severity of anthropogenic pollution. The regions where the xenobiotic content in the blood of permanent residents did not exceed ≥ 5.0 mcg/dl were conventionally named a low-level anthropogenically polluted regions. (The first target group of the study), and the regions where the level of xenobiotics in the blood of permanently residing adolescents exceeded ≤ 10.0 mcg/dl were named a low-level anthropogenically polluted regions (the second target group of the study).

The control group included a contingent without xenobiotics in their blood. Xenobiotics were identified in the blood of target and control group adolescents by atomic adsorption method [4], data processing was performed using IBM SPSS - 25.0 computer software. Testing of motor system and attention functioning of the target and controls group was done according to the Luria-Christensen method (Luria version) [5]. Visual-motor and visual-space testing was done using WBAVMA [6].

Age and gender data of target and control groups

I Target group N=32		II Target group N=41		III Target group N=28	
Age					
Age 19-21		Age 22-23		Age 20-23	
B	G	B	G	B	G
19	13	24	17	15	13

Results. According to the Visual Motor (WBAVMA) data (hidden, camouflaged and real features, motor tasks, fine motor movements, as well as voluntary movement target orientation (during active behaviour), the data of the first target group and control group are similar ($P > 0.05$) and much better compared to the second target group ($P < 0.01$). No gender difference was detected. At the same time, the contingent of the second target group often made mistakes while performing motor tasks (according to gender data, the group of boys - 24%, girls - 18%). The gender difference ($P < 0.05$) is probably related to the orientation expressed during their voluntary movements and tasks. Coordination (right and left hand) in the first target group was much more sophisticated ($P < 0.01$) compared to the second target group and did not differ from the control group. In addition, sub-testing of petty (fine) motor movements revealed age and gender differences. The gender difference in the contingent of the first target group was more conveyed compared to the second target group.

Conclusions. Symptoms of attention deficit disorder and motor disorders in adolescents permanently residing in anthropogenically low-level polluted regions are clinically much simpler than in adults permanently residing in anthropogenically high-level polluted regions and are manifested without elements of hyperactivity. Attention deficit (mild form) in adolescents

permanently residing in highly anthropogenically polluted regions is more similar to the cerebrospinal variant and differs significantly from the clinical picture of attention (low anthropogenic contamination data). In the social-behavioral aspect, interpersonal attention and communication are homogeneous in both target groups and are practically similar to the control group data. The level of anthropogenic contamination with xenobiotic in different Georgian Regions is variable.

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